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ARTÍCULO DE INVESTIGACIÓN

Investigación y gestión de iniciativas innovadoras en educación: aspecto metodológico

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Resumen

En el artículo se determina el grado de desarrollo del problema de la formación de docentes orientada a la innovación en la educación profesional adicional en la teoría y la práctica, una visión sistemática del objeto y tema de investigación en el contexto de las principales tendencias en el desarrollo de se forma la educación. A partir de un análisis comparativo de las innovaciones científicas presentadas, se aclaró la esencia del concepto de "innovación pedagógica", se identificaron y fundamentaron las particularidades de la educación orientada a la innovación. Se han desarrollado las bases conceptuales de una gestión pedagógica orientada a la innovación. Se han desarrollado enfoques metodológicos y fundamentos organizativos-pedagógicos de la formación en la formación profesional del profesorado para la gestión pedagógica.

Palabras clave: innovación pedagógica, fundamentos pedagógicos, necesidades de formación profesional, gestión pedagógica.

Abstract

Research and management of innovative initiatives in education: methodological aspect

In the article, the degree of development of the problem of innovation-oriented training of teachers in additional professional education in theory and practice is determined, a systematic view of the object and subject of research in the context of the leading trends in the development of education is formed. On the basis of a comparative analysis of the

scientific innovations presented, the essence of the concept of "pedagogical innovation" has been clarified, the specifics of innovation-oriented education have been identified and substantiated. The conceptual foundations of innovatively oriented pedagogical management have been developed. Methodological approaches and organizational-pedagogical foundations of training in the professional education of teaching staff for pedagogical management have been developed.

Keywords: pedagogical innovation, pedagogical foundations, professional education needs, pedagogical management.

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1. Introduction

The modern education system, subject to the requirements of the time, is experiencing a period of rapid development of innovative activity. During this process arose the contradiction between the rapidly changing content of education and the improvement of educational management that lags behind it.

Solving this problem should lead to a change in the system of intra-school management and the creation of a set of management innovations that contribute to the development of the school.

The development of even the most advanced and promising pedagogical innovations, given the low quality of management activities, cannot be widely and effectively introduced into educational practice. The more complex the innovation, the more complex the tasks of managing its dissemination and adoption, the less likely it is to be accepted by practice. Without professionalization of education management in modern the scientific base has to overcome the difficulties that arise by the subjects of innovation activity themselves.

In this situation, the importance of targeted training of teaching staff for the development and implementation of innovations, for managing innovation processes, increases sharply, primarily at the most important level of education - at the level of an educational institution. Traditionally, training on certain problems of professional activity is carried out in the system of additional professional education, primarily in various forms of advanced training.

However, at present this system is in the stage of active transformation, the need for which is due to objective changes in the conditions of its functioning.

In a market economy, the system of financing advanced training for teachers is undergoing significant transformation, as a result of which the usual forms of periodic course training at universities and advanced training institutes are gradually becoming a thing of the past. In addition, course preparation, as a rule, divorced from the practical problems of students, ceases to meet the needs of their real professional development. This necessitates the search for new forms and methods of teaching in the system of additional education, new approaches to organizing the educational process that fully meet modern trends in the development of society, educational sphere, as well as the needs of the individual.

From this point of view, the training of teaching staff in the system of continuous professional education, primarily heads of educational institutions, purposefully focused on innovation activities, on managing innovation processes, acquires special significance, since not only level of professionalism of education workers, but also efficiency innovative pedagogical activity, and, therefore, the prospects for the development of education, the possibility of its qualitative renewal.

This determines the social and pedagogical relevance of the problem of organizing innovation-oriented training of teaching staff for intra-school management in continuing professional education, built on the basis of new methodological approaches that are adequate to modern trends in the development of society and the needs of the individual.

2. Methodology

At the same time, the analysis of these works shows that the problems of targeted systematic training of educators for innovation activities and management of innovation processes, primarily at the secondary school level, have not yet become the subject of special research.

The solution to this problem, in turn, cannot be considered in isolation from the problems of improving intra-school management, which are of utmost importance from the point of view of school renewal in accordance with the defining trends of social development and are comprehensively studied in pedagogy. A significant contribution to the study of this issue was made by (Korthagen, F. A. J., 2004), (Meyer, H., 2010), (Novoa, A., 2017), (Sahlberg, P., 2011), (Wenger, E., 1998), (Biesta, G., 2015), (Day, C., 2004), (Niemi, H., & Nevgi, A., 2014) et al., whose research led to the formation of new approaches to management, conceptualized as pedagogical management. However, in the studied works, questions related to innovation management as a specific component of management activities in education are, at best, only posed, but not deeply and comprehensively studied. This determines the third aspect problems of innovation-oriented training of teaching staff in the system of continuous professional education, important from the point of view of its goals and content.

In general, today we can only say that objectively various studies have laid the foundation for its solution.

Many problems have only been identified, possible approaches to them have been outlined solution, but scientific research devoted to a comprehensive, systematic consideration of the methodological, theoretical, organizational, pedagogical and technological foundations of teacher training personnel for innovation activities and innovation management in the system of continuous professional education are missing, although this problem is recognized as one of the most pressing in pedagogy. This determines the scientific relevance of the problem we are studying.

Thus, a contradiction has arisen between the need for targeted training of teaching staff to manage innovative processes in the system of continuous professional training education and insufficient development of its theoretical, methodological, organizational and pedagogical foundations.

Resolving this contradiction requires research into the following main aspects of the problem field:

- consideration of innovative processes in education in the context of modern trends in social development and educational development, identification of the socio-pedagogical significance of educational innovations, their essential characteristics that ensure the stability and productivity of innovative processes;
- identifying the specifics and conceptual foundations of pedagogical management, purposefully focused on managing innovation and innovation processes;
- consideration of the methodological, organizational and pedagogical foundations of training teaching staff in vocational education to manage innovation processes.

In accordance with this, the purpose of the article is determined - to develop and scientifically substantiate the methodological, conceptual-theoretical and organizational-pedagogical foundations of innovation-oriented preparation for pedagogical management in vocational education.

The object of the article is continuous professional education.

The subject of the article is the process of innovation-oriented training of teachers for pedagogical management.

Hypothesis of the article. Training of teaching staff for pedagogical management in vocational education will have an innovative focus if:

- innovative processes in education are considered as objectively determined by global trends in social development at the present stage and have strategic importance for the formation of post-industrial society;
- management of innovation processes is conceptualized as a specific component of management activities, causing qualitative changes in all the main components of the management system of an educational institution;

- the basis for constructing a teacher training model in continuing professional education is based on principles that ensure the permanence and activity-based practical orientation of training, and the inclusion of students in an innovative environment;

- methodologically, the organization of teacher training is built on the basis of approaches that make it possible to flexibly and quickly identify the needs of students and satisfy them in adequate organizational forms;

- the pedagogical training process structurally not only ensures the formation of the personal and professional readiness of each teacher for innovative activities, but also acts as a factor in innovative transformations in educational institutions and the regional (municipal) educational system as a whole;

- an indicator of the effectiveness of training is real innovative changes in the management system of educational institutions, systematically covering all its main components.

To solve assigned problems and check hypotheses, the study used a complex of theoretical and experimental methods and techniques that are adequate to the nature of the object being studied:

- methods of theoretical analysis, synthesis, abstraction and generalization, which were used in a comprehensive study of various scientific views on the research problem, reflected in scientific sources, as well as when comprehending practical experience;

- a system-structural method, which made it possible to consider the phenomena being studied in all the diversity, interconnectedness and integral unity of their components;

- modeling method used for a visual description of system objects;

- complex empirical methods (pedagogical monitoring, pedagogical experiment);

- private empirical methods (observation, questioning, testing, expert assessment) used to diagnose and analyze the state of the phenomenon being studied;

- methods of statistical processing of experimental research results.

3. Results

The scientific novelty of the article lies in the formulation and solution of the problem of organizing innovation-oriented preparation for pedagogical management in vocational education, which became the subject of a special scientific study, during which:

- the essence of innovation-oriented education is revealed, representing a content-specific area of specialist training, ensuring their professional readiness to develop and implement innovations, manage innovation processes in their field of activity, which

must be considered as a transitional stage in the movement towards an innovative education system, towards an innovative society;

- the specifics of innovation-oriented pedagogical management as an intra-school management system that ensures the transition of an educational institution to a development mode on the basis of a coordinated restructuring of all its main components (conceptual, organizational-structural, functional-managerial, technological, personal-professional) in accordance with the strategic goals of establishing an innovative education and innovative society;

- the principles of constructing an innovative model for training teaching staff to manage innovations in education are highlighted and justified: ensuring systemic integration of knowledge, ensuring the activity-based and practical orientation of knowledge, focus on formation of an innovative culture, group training, development of pedagogical potential;

- a structural model of innovation-oriented personnel training for pedagogical management in continuing professional education has been developed, including target, content, organizational, structural, technological and effective components, ensuring not only a personal result, but also a social effect, since the result of training is actually become: the individual's readiness to manage innovation processes; readiness of the educational institution for innovative activities; readiness of the educational system for innovative development;

- the optimality of implementing a model of innovation-oriented personnel training for pedagogical management is substantiated on the basis of a project-coordination approach as a method of organizational activity aimed at transforming reality through the coordinated development and implementation of a number of projects united by a common goal.

The theoretical significance of the article lies in the fact that the results obtained represent the theoretical and methodological foundations systemic innovation-oriented training of teaching staff for pedagogical management and thereby contribute to the development of pedagogical science, namely:

- the essence and content of the concepts are clarified: innovation-oriented education, pedagogical innovation, pedagogical innovation, innovation-oriented pedagogical management, which contributes to the development of the conceptual and terminological apparatus of pedagogy and education;

- the developed conceptual foundations of innovative pedagogical management make it possible to design the goals, content and technologies for managing innovations in education, ensuring a qualitative change in education in accordance with modern sociocultural guidelines for the development of society and the individual;

- the essential characteristics of the project-coordination approach to organizing the training of teaching staff for innovative management in the system of vocational education, which meets the strategic goals and trends in the formation of an innovative

society and innovative education, are highlighted, which is a contribution to the development of pedagogical methodology;

- the identified general conceptual and theoretical foundations of innovation-oriented training of teaching staff make a certain contribution to the theory of general and vocational education,

since they provide the opportunity for further comprehensive research in the field of innovation-oriented education;

- the developed technological support for innovation-oriented training in vocational education contributes to the development of educational technologies.

The practical significance of the article is determined by the development in the course of an experimental study of technological support, which can be used as a scientifically based means of innovation-oriented preparation for pedagogical management in vocational education and includes technologies:

- preparation and conduct of pedagogical readings, innovation forum and other major scientific and methodological events;

- conducting year-long scientific and methodological seminars for educational practitioners;

- analysis of problems and planning on this basis for the management of scientific and methodological work in an educational institution;

- development of a self-management program for teachers and managers in an educational institution;

- development of a target program for the development of the municipal education system, educational institution;

- development of a municipal innovative educational system.

This technological support, with the necessary substantive adjustments, can also be used when organizing professional training for specialists in other profiles and areas.

4. Discussion

An analysis of numerous scientific sources allows us to state that over the past twenty years, innovative activity in the educational sphere, which arose largely spontaneously, has acquired a large-scale character, which allows us to speak not just about the spread of innovations in education, but about the formation of an innovation movement (Niemi, H., & Nevgi, A., 2014). At the same time, researchers note that this movement is currently experiencing a crisis, which indicates primarily the need to manage innovative processes in education.

The management strategy has also been quite clearly defined, due to the fact that in modern society innovations, which have become widespread in almost all spheres of

activity, are becoming the most important, universal factor in managed social development.

That is why the innovative path of development is proclaimed by the governments of the most developed countries of the world as one of the defining strategies of public administration (Korthagen, F. A. J., 2004). Moreover, this process has a clear tendency to move to the global stage - an innovative path of development of the entire civilization, the formation of an innovative society.

The formation of an innovative society inevitably places certain demands on education, which in the modern world not only requires improvement - it must become innovative in its essence. The renewal of the world and society sets innovative processes in education are characterized by the nature of permanence, continuity, focus on constant essential and holistic renewal of the educational process (Meyer, H., 2010). And although it is still too early to talk about the formation of an innovative education system in our country, it is obvious that at the present stage of development of domestic education within the framework innovation movement, an innovation-oriented education is being formed - a transitional stage in the movement towards an innovative education system.

Today, innovation-oriented education is a content-specific area of training specialists, ensuring their professional readiness to develop and implement innovations, manage innovation processes in their field of activity. Of particular relevance from this point of view is the innovation-oriented training of teaching staff, which will overcome the spontaneity of the innovation movement in education and transfer the processes of development and implementation of pedagogical innovations into a controlled, professional direction (Novoa, A., 2017). And innovation-oriented continuous professional education is of paramount importance, i.e. the training of educators who are already directly involved in innovative transformations in the pedagogical sphere.

At the initial stage of its development, one of the most important areas of research into innovation processes that covered the field of education was the problem of systematization of innovations. By different researchers various classifications of innovations in education have been proposed (Sahlberg, P., 2011). Today, this problem, taking into account the essence of innovation as a social phenomenon generated by the global trend of social development at the stage of transition to a post-industrial innovative society, acquires a relevant and important aspect of differentiation, the essential distinction between pedagogical innovations and pedagogical innovations themselves.

From this point of view, by pedagogical innovations we understand innovations in educational activities that are caused by evolutionary changes in social needs and, accordingly, educational goals, the continuous development of educational means and technologies. Such innovations are inevitable in the process of permanent modernization of education, since they express its continuous development.

In contrast, pedagogical innovations are innovations that express paradigmatic changes in the development of education, caused by significant sociocultural

transformations that change the very social function of education. The current stage in the development of domestic education is precisely such a stage, characterized by radical and radical searches.

Another relevant aspect of research in pedagogical innovation is related to the development of scientific foundations for managing innovation processes, which are of key importance for the practice of educational activities today (Tatto, M. T. (Ed.), 2015). The interdisciplinary nature of innovation, innovative activity and management of innovative processes necessitates the use of an integrative methodological approach, combining the methodology of different sciences, in the process of their research in pedagogy. From this point of view, of decisive importance are general scientific methods (systemic, synergetic approaches), sociological methods (resource approach), methods of innovation management theory (factorial, functional, situational approaches), psychological methods (personal-activity approach), pedagogical methods (person-oriented, competence-based, cultural, axiological). Only such a holistic, integrated approach will avoid one-sidedness in understanding the essence of pedagogical innovations and the process of managing them.

In the process of reforming and modernizing domestic education, management issues have become extremely relevant at all levels of the educational system - from managing the country's education system as a whole to managing the specific process of training and education of an individual. This is dictated, on the one hand, by the need to bring the content and forms of management activities in the field of education into line with the needs of a changing society and trends in social development (social aspect), and on the other hand, by the need to enrich the theory and practice of education management with the achievements of scientific management, which has been developed at the end of the 20th century (theoretical and methodological aspect).

In general, the development of ideas about the nature of intra-school management can be rightfully considered as a transition from administrative-authoritarian management to pedagogical management. In this context, in contrast to the traditional organizational and management system of the school, which provided for the presence of certain structural units (in accordance with the type and type of institution, number of students, number of classes), corresponding functional responsibilities, strict administrative methods of management, the subjects of which were director and his deputies, today the school is viewed as a complex developing and evolving dynamic system with an expanded subject of management.

From the standpoint of pedagogical management in the system of intra-school management, it is advisable and necessary to highlight the following blocks, the interaction of which ensures the effectiveness of the functioning of the management system: conceptual (the concept of intra-school management); organizational-structural (organizational management structure); functional-managerial (functional composition of management); technological (control mechanism); personal and professional (requirements of pedagogical management for the personal and professional qualities of modern heads of educational institutions).

One of the mandatory components of an effective intra-school management system is self-management - a system of ways of human activity that allows you to make the most of your own capabilities, consciously and rationally manage your life, actively and effectively influence external circumstances at work and in your personal life for your own purposes.

The relevance for the pedagogical sphere of this special scientific direction in management, designed to increase the efficiency of human activity to achieve his personal and professional goals, is due to the fact that research indicates the presence of serious problems in the area of teachers' organization of their work. Self-management technology, which takes into account the specific features of the educational system, including the presence of managers at different levels within one educational institution, makes it possible to optimize labor and time costs, obtain time reserves for the development and self-development of teachers and managers, which directly contributes to increased quality of educational services (Wenger, E., 1998).

The need to ensure the stability of the process of creating and implementing innovations, developing criteria for determining their prospects and effectiveness, identifying the most optimal conditions for their implementation, organizing this process and managing it led to the emergence of innovation management - one of the relatively young, but actively developing applied sciences, accumulating concepts and technological developments on problems of managing innovation processes, creation and implementation of innovations. Innovative management involves a clear distinction between different management functions, different organizational structures and different organizational mechanisms, depending on the object of management, which can be either the functioning or development of the organization (Biesta, G., 2015). These two "vectors" in the organization's activities are in many ways alternative, since one (functioning) is aimed at stabilizing organizational processes, and the other (development) is aimed at changing them, and therefore destruction, destabilization.

Innovative activity in a modern school is one of the aspects of its work in the development mode, which is understood as the sequence of certain stages of the process leading to positive qualitative changes in results determined by goal setting.

Actions aimed at ensuring the organization and purposefulness of innovative processes in school are precisely development management, as a result of the implementation of the functions of which decisions are developed aimed at qualitative changes in the content, technology, organization of the educational process and its support. Based on this criterion, it is possible to determine what is being done in management for development from what is being done to maintain stable functioning (Menter, I., et al., 2010).

From these positions, the ability and readiness of the management system to carry out innovative processes in an educational institution determine the following qualitative changes in its main components - blocks of the intra-school management system:

- conceptual - its innovative focus is expressed by the concept of intra-school management, which is based on a certain idea of school development;

- organizational and structural - involves the creation of an organizational management structure that ensures the prompt implementation of management innovations and pedagogical innovations in the school's activities, the flexible response of all structural units and personnel to the changes introduced;
- functional-managerial - organization of management activities at all levels based on methods of situational management and results-based management;
- technological - the use of innovative educational technologies adequate to the goals of school development;
- personal-professional - ensured by the professional-personal readiness of educational institution leaders and teachers to manage innovative processes on the basis of self-management.

The last block is largely decisive, since it is the personal and professional readiness of school leaders and teachers for innovative activities that becomes the key, the main condition for the readiness of the intra-school management system to ensure the continuity and reproducibility of innovative processes in an educational institution.

The need for continuous innovation-oriented professional development and training of teaching staff working in the field of education today poses the problem of organizing their targeted regular training for innovative activities. Systematic, conceptually structured training of personnel on certain current problems of professional activity is traditionally carried out within the framework of the system of additional professional education, which is currently in the stage of active development, the search for new forms and technologies of training that are most adequate to the modern needs of society as a whole and each individual, strategically oriented towards the transition from a discrete to a self-adjusting state-social system of continuous education, which has an extensive network of educational structures, various flexible forms and methods of teaching.

Research shows that today the main goal of the system of advanced training for teachers is a qualitative change in pedagogical activity in the field of the educational process, and it also acts as the main indicator of the effectiveness of their training in the system of additional professional education (Zeichner, K., & Liston, D., 2013). This, in turn, requires further search and application of fundamentally new, innovative approaches to the problem of advanced training of teaching staff, including in the aspect of their preparation for innovative activities and management of innovative processes in education.

Summarizing the innovative searches of researchers in this direction, we can highlight the principles of constructing an innovative training model teaching staff, which must be met by their training in continuous professional education, focused on training to innovation activities:

- ensuring systemic integration of knowledge, including the entire spectrum of diverse types of knowledge in their interdependence: theoretical, empirical, personal, interpersonal, intuitive, special, current, etc.;

- ensuring the activity-practical orientation of knowledge by maximizing the use of the entire activity potential of knowledge to ensure its practical application in educational activities in the interests of every teacher, every educational institution, as well as the development of the educational system as a whole;

- focus on the formation of an innovative culture as the assimilation of professional norms and values that orient all educators towards the development of the educational system, its innovative transformation and uniting them into a single pedagogical community;

- group learning, providing extraordinary opportunities for coordinated action, as well as individual development through dialogue and "shared thinking." Within the framework of additional professional education, forms of group training can include conferences, seminars, master classes, pedagogical workshops, round tables, etc.;

- development of pedagogical potential. In accordance with this principle, training should not just provide advanced training for individual educators in some areas professional activities, but to promote the development of the professional pedagogical potential of students as a condition for the development of the pedagogical potential of the educational system (city, municipal, regional, etc.) as a whole (Day, C., 2004). Only in this case does the personal development of each individual become focused on achieving common, collective, corporate goals of the entire pedagogical community within the educational system.

The innovative nature of the educational model for training teachers for innovation activities and management of innovative processes, built on the basis of the identified principles, necessitates the use of adequate methodological approaches to its development and implementation in educational practice. Modeling itself is one of the most productive methods for studying and transforming systems, an important component of the systems approach.

In our study, modeling is of a design nature, which determines the expediency of using the design method.

The structural model of innovation-oriented personnel training for pedagogical management in continuing professional education determines the specifics of its components, which include:

- Target component: expresses the purpose of training - the formation of practical readiness of heads of educational institutions and teachers to manage innovative processes.

- Subjective component: in the traditional system of advanced training, teaching subjects and trained subjects are clearly separated by their positions in the pedagogical process; in an innovation model, built on the mutual exchange of innovative experience, the position of the subject can change - in one case he acts as a student, in another, as someone who has experience in innovative activities, he can become a teacher himself (Darling-Hammond, L., & Lieberman, A. (Eds.), 2012).

- Content component: the specificity of the training content is that it covers almost all the problems of modern education, since they are related in one way or another to innovation, and the thematic sequence of continuous training is determined the needs of students identified during the learning process.

- Organizational and structural component: reflects the forms of training, which in the innovative model, along with traditional course forms, include:

- scientific and practical conferences and seminars that provide conditions for scientific analysis of one's own innovative activities, generalization of its results in the form of a report, public presentation

them in the form of a speech, mutual exchange of scientifically meaningful innovative experience and its collective discussion, publication of results;

- forms of group learning (master classes, pedagogical workshops, etc.), ensuring the active involvement of all participants in the learning process, exchange of knowledge and experience;

- consultations with specialists as a form of individual training.

Technological component: ensures the use of educational means, methods and technologies of training that meet the specific goals and content of the innovation model.

Effective component: an innovative model aimed at obtaining a personal result also provides a social effect, since the result of training actually becomes:

- readiness of the individual to manage innovation processes;

- readiness of the educational institution for innovative activities;

- readiness of the educational system for innovative development.

This fully meets the strategic development goals of the country, which orient social development towards the formation of a national innovation system.

5. Conclusions

Thus, innovation-oriented education is a content-specific direction in the training of specialists, ensuring their professional readiness to develop and implement innovations, manage innovation processes in their field of activity, which must be considered as a transitional stage in the movement towards an innovative education system, towards an innovative society. Pedagogical innovations are innovations expressing paradigmatic changes in the development of education, caused by significant sociocultural transformations that change the very social function of education, in contrast to pedagogical innovations, which are caused by evolutionary changes in social needs and, accordingly, educational goals, and the continuous development of educational means and technologies. The purposeful systematic orientation of the management system towards innovation activities is ensured by innovation-oriented pedagogical management, representing is a system of intra-school management that ensures the

transition of an educational institution to a development mode based on the coordinated restructuring of all its main components in accordance with strategic goals for the development of innovative education and innovative society. The ability and readiness of the management system to carry out innovative processes in an educational institution determine the following qualitative changes to its main components – blocks.

Intra-school management systems:

a) conceptual - its innovative focus is expressed by the concept of intra-school management, which is based on a certain idea of school development;

b) organizational and structural - involves the creation of an organizational management structure that ensures the prompt implementation of management innovations and pedagogical innovations in activities schools, flexible response of all structural units and personnel to introduced changes;

c) functional-managerial - organization of management activities at all levels based on methods of situational management and results-based management;

d) technological - the use of innovative educational technologies that are adequate to the goals;

e) personal-professional - ensured by the professional-personal readiness of educational institution leaders and teachers to manage innovative processes on the basis of self-management. This block is decisive, since it is the personal and professional readiness of school leaders and teachers for innovative activities that becomes the key, the main condition for the readiness of the intra-school management system to ensure continuity and reproducibility of innovative processes in an educational institution. The conceptual and organizing principles in developing a model for training teaching staff in continuous professional education for innovative activities are the following principles:

- ensuring systemic integration of knowledge, including the entire spectrum of diverse types of knowledge in their interdependence: theoretical, empirical, personal, interpersonal, intuitive, special, current, etc.;

Ensuring the activity-practical orientation of knowledge by maximizing the use of the entire activity potential of knowledge to ensure its practical application in educational activities in the interests of every teacher, every educational institution, as well as the development of the educational system as a whole;

Focus on the formation of an innovative culture as the assimilation of professional norms and values that orient all educators towards the development of the educational system, its innovative transformation and uniting them into a single pedagogical community;

- group learning, providing extraordinary opportunities for coordinated action, as well as individual development based on dialogue and "shared thinking" and taking the form of conferences, seminars, master classes, pedagogical workshops, round tables, etc.;

- development of the pedagogical potential of students as a condition for the development of the pedagogical potential of the educational system (city, municipal, regional, etc.) as a whole.

The structural model of innovation-oriented personnel training for pedagogical management in continuing professional education determines the specifics of its components, which include:

a) target component: expresses the goal of training - the formation of practical readiness of heads of educational institutions and teachers to manage innovative processes;

b) subject component: in the traditional system of advanced training, teaching subjects and trained subjects are clearly separated by their positions in the pedagogical process; in an innovation model, built on the mutual exchange of innovative experience, the position of the subject can change - in one case he acts as a student, in another, as someone who has experience in innovative activities, he can become a teacher himself;

c) content component: the specificity of the training content is that it covers almost all the problems of modern education, since they are somehow related to innovation, and the thematic sequence of continuous training is determined the needs of students identified during the learning process;

d) organizational and structural component: reflects the forms of training, which in the innovation model, along with traditional course forms, include: scientific and practical conferences and seminars that provide conditions for scientific analysis of one's own innovative activities, generalization of its results in the form of a report, public presentation of them in the form speeches, mutual exchange of scientifically meaningful innovative experience and its collective discussion, publication of results; forms of group learning (master classes, pedagogical workshops, etc.) that ensure active involvement all participants in the learning process, exchange of knowledge and experience; consultations with specialists as a form of individual training;

e) technological component: ensures the use of educational means, methods and technologies of training that meet the specific goals and content of the innovation model;

f) effective component: an innovation model aimed at obtaining a personal result also provides a social effect, since the result of training actually becomes: the individual's readiness to manage innovative processes; readiness of the educational institution for innovative activities; readiness of the educational system for innovative development.

The most optimal methodological tools for constructing an innovative model for training teaching staff for management of innovative processes in education is a project-coordination approach, which is a method of organizational activity aimed at transforming reality through the coordinated development and implementation of a number of projects united by a common goal.

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